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Biochemical Effects of Tramadol Administration on Total Protein, Albumin and Globulin During Sub-Chronic Alcoholic Beverage (Lager beer) Consumption in Wistar Rats

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated Tramadol, a pain-relieving drug used for the management of moderate to severe pain in adults. When used continuously over a long period of time, in combination with substances like alcohol, or in overdose, it results in serious health challenges. This study is aimed at determining the biochemical effects of Tramadol administration during sub-chronic alcoholic beverage (lager beer) administration in mature Wistar rats. Twenty-four (24) male adult Wistar rats weighing an average of 120 g were obtained and divided into four groups of six rats each. Group one, the normal control, received 0.5 ml of water; group two received Tramadol (1.43 mg/kg b.w.); group three was given lager beer (34.29 ml/kg b.w.); and group four was given a combination of Tramadol + lager beer (1.43 mg/kg + 34.29 ml/kg b.w.) orally. The administration was done once daily for 21 days. At the end of the 21 days, the animals were fasted overnight, weighed, and anaesthetized using ketamine, then dissected. Blood samples were collected via cardiac puncture into plain tubes, allowed to stand for 2 hours, and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to obtain serum used for biochemical assays. The results obtained showed a reduction in growth and body weight increase in the administered groups compared to the control. Globulin and protein concentrations reduced in the Tramadol-only group, while albumin reduced in all the groups compared to the control. Significant increases in serum globulin levels

were recorded in the groups treated with lager beer and Tramadol + lager beer compared to the group treated with Tramadol alone. In conclusion, the toxic effects of Tramadol are enhanced when administered in combination with sub-chronic alcoholic beverage (lager beer) administration in Wistar rats.

Keywords: Tramadol, Alcohol, Liver function, Kidney function, Oxidative stress, Wistar rats

1. INTRODUCTION

Tramadol is a synthetic opioid analgesic used in the management of moderate to severe pain. It acts centrally by binding to the μ -opioid receptor and inhibiting the reuptake of serotonin and norepinephrine, thereby altering pain perception (Grond & Sablotzki, 2004). It was first synthesized by Grünenthal GmbH in Germany in the late 1970s as a safer alternative to traditional opioids such as morphine. Tramadol is marketed under various brand names, including Ultram, Tramal, and Contramal.

Tramadol has a dual mechanism of action: it acts as a weak μ -opioid receptor agonist and inhibits the reuptake of serotonin and norepinephrine, which enhances descending inhibitory pain pathways (Raffa et al., 1992). Its analgesic efficacy and relatively lower abuse potential compared to conventional opioids led to its widespread use. However, misuse and abuse of tramadol have been reported globally, especially among young adults seeking euphoric or stimulant effects (Adeloye et al., 2019).

Figure 1. Mechanism of action of tramadol.

Oxidative stress is a condition characterised by an imbalance between the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the antioxidant defence mechanisms of the body. Excess ROS can damage lipids, proteins, and nucleic acids, leading to impaired cellular functions. Biomarkers such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), reduced glutathione (GSH), and malondialdehyde (MDA) are often measured to assess oxidative stress levels (Halliwell & Gutteridge, 2015). Although several studies have investigated the individual effects of tramadol and alcohol on organ function and oxidative stress, limited research exists on their combined effects. This study, therefore, examines the impact of tramadol, lager beer, and their combination on body weight, liver and kidney function parameters, and oxidative stress indices in male Wistar albino rats.

Figure 3. Tramadol (1S, 2S)

Total protein

Total protein refers to the sum of all proteins present in plasma or serum. Proteins play vital roles in maintaining osmotic balance, transporting molecules, and serving as enzymes and structural components. The normal range of total protein in serum is typically 6.0–8.3 g/dL (Tietz, 1995). Alterations in total protein levels may indicate impaired liver function, kidney disease, or malnutrition.

Albumin

Albumin is the most abundant plasma protein, synthesised in the liver, and constitutes about 60% of total plasma protein. It plays a major role in maintaining colloid osmotic pressure and in the transport of various endogenous and exogenous substances, including hormones, fatty acids, and drugs. Low levels of serum albumin (hypoalbuminemia) may result from chronic liver disease, nephrotic syndrome, or malnutrition, while elevated levels (hyperalbuminaemia) are rare and often due to dehydration (Busher, 1990).

Globulin

Globulins comprise a heterogeneous group of proteins, including immunoglobulins, enzymes, and transport proteins. They are divided into α_1 , α_2 , β , and γ fractions.

The concentration of globulins is often estimated by subtracting albumin from total protein using the formula:

$$\text{Globulin} = \text{Total Protein} - \text{Albumin}$$

Globulin concentrations are usually expressed in grams per litre (g/L) or milligrams per decilitre (mg/dL). Elevated globulin levels may occur in chronic infections, autoimmune diseases, and certain malignancies, while reduced levels may indicate immunodeficiency or liver dysfunction (Busher, 1990).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Collection and Preparation of Materials

Budweiser lager beer (5% Alc) was obtained from Coslow store along MCC road Calabar and was used as alcoholic beverage. Tramadol (50 mg) was obtained with prescription from Maxi-care Pharmacy in Calabar.

2. 2. Laboratory Animals

Twenty-four (24) *Wistar* rats weighing 83.24g to 118.92g were obtained from the animal house of the College of Medical Sciences, University of Calabar. The animals were housed in aluminium cages in the animal house, and fed with rat chow and tap water *ad libitum*. The animals were acclimatized for seven days and their weights noted before the commencement of the experimental treatment.

2. 3. Experimental Protocol

The animals were divided into four groups of six rats each and treated as shown in tables.

2. 4. Drug Administration

The twenty-four rats were divided into four groups of six rats each. Group one served as the normal control and received 0.5 ml of water, group two received tramadol (1.43 mg/kg body weight), group three was given alcoholic beverage dose lager beer (34.29 ml/kg) and group four was given (1.43 mg/kg body weight of tramadol) + lager beer (34.29 ml/kg body weight). The administration was carried out once daily for 21 days.

2. 5. Collection and Preparation of Sample for Analysis

At the end of the 21 days, the animals were fasted overnight and anaesthetized using ketamine. They were then dissected and their blood collected with sterile syringes by cardiac puncture. The blood was divided into two fractions; one fraction was collected into heparinised screw-cap bottles for haematological analysis. Samples in the plain tubes were allowed to stand for two hours for clotting to take place. The samples were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes using an MSE table top centrifuge. Serum was collected using semi-automatic micro-pipette into labelled specimen tubes. The serum was stored in a refrigerator until when required for analysis. The storage period however did not exceed 48 hours.

2. 6. Materials/Apparatus

Beakers, centrifuge-tubes, orogastric tubes, pipettes, heparinised screw-cap tubes, fume chamber, measuring scientific equipment centrifuge, cuvettes and haematocrit reader, light microscope, spectrophotometer. Reagents kits for the determination of aspartate amino-transferase, alanine amino-transferase, alkaline phosphatase, urea, creatinine, bilirubin and total protein were obtained from the Department of Chemical Pathology, University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH), Calabar. Reagents used for the estimation of haematological indices were obtained from the Department of Haematology, University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH). Reagents for tissue preservation and histological staining were obtained from the Department of Histopathology, University of Calabar, Teaching Hospital (UCTH), Calabar. Reagent kits for the determination of lipid profile, serum electrolytes and serum antioxidants were also obtained from the Department of Chemical Pathology, University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH), Calabar. Moreso, reagent kits used for the histopathological examination of the liver and kidney were obtained from the Department of Histopathology, University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH), Calabar.

Table 1. Experimental group distribution of *Wistar* rats during treatment with tramadol and alcoholic beverage (lager beer)

Groups	Number of Animals	Treatment
1	6	Normal control (0.5 ml water)
2	6	Tramadol (1.43 mg/kg body weight)
3	6	Lager beer (34.29 ml/kg body weight)
4	6	Tramadol plus lager beer (1.43 mg plus 34.29 ml/kg body weight)

2. 7. Protein Estimation (g/L)

Total protein (g/L) was estimated based on the interaction of cupric ions, in an alkaline medium with protein peptide bonds to form a coloured compound.

In the copper ion based protein assays, protein solutions are mixed with an alkaline solution of copper salt, (cupric ions, Cu^{2+}). The protein assay is based on the interaction of cupric ions with protein in an alkaline solution and is commonly referred to as the Biuret assay. The interaction of cupric ions (Cu^{2+}) with protein results in a purple colour that can be read at 540 nm. The amount of colour produced is proportional to protein concentration.

Principle

Biuret is a small compound that forms when urea is heated to allowing two urea molecules to join. Urea molecules fused in this manner produce amide groups (-NH) at the centre of the molecule which bind to cupric ions at a basic pH. The copper complexes that result from this interaction produce a strong blue colour that can be measured with a

spectrophotometer. Proteins also contain amide groups. When an amino group and a carboxyl group join to form a peptide bond, the amino group (-NH₂) becomes an amide group (-NH). At basic pH, the proteins forms complex with copper ions. Because this reaction was first observed with biuret, it is called the biuret reaction, and when this reaction is used to measure protein concentrations, it is called the Biuret Protein Assay (Herriott, R.M. 2014).

Thus, in this assay you will combine protein samples with Biuret Reagent which contains copper ions in a basic solution. The copper ions will complex with the amide groups in the proteins to create a blue colour that will be measured using a spectrophotometer. The intensity of the colour formed is directly proportional to the number of peptide bonds participating in the reaction and thus in the amount of protein present.

Figure 4. Reaction of Biuret and copper complex, B. Biuret reagent reacts with an alkaline solution of CuSO₄ to form a violet chelate compound.

This relationship allows a standard curve to be created that is used to calculate the concentration of protein in an unknown sample.

Procedure

A stock solution of BSA protein was prepared (10 mg/ml) and kept in a labelled beaker. 150 ml of Biuret reagent was made by proper measuring cylinder. In the test tube, dilution of proteins was made with different volume from the stock by mixing appropriate amount of BSA stock and water as mentioned in 4 ml of Biuret reagent is added to all the test tube. In another test tube, 1 ml of unknown sample is taken and 4 ml of Biuret reagent is added to it. Incubate all the test tubes for 30 minutes at room temperature. Set dark zero and blank zero of spectrophotometer and leave it for 20-30 minutes. After completion of incubation time. Take the absorbance reading by placing the sample in the spectrophotometer.

2. 8. Albumin Estimation (g/L)

Serum albumin at pH.4.2 binds with BCG to form a blue coloured compound. The blue colour formed is directly proportional to the concentration of albumin.

Albumin is generally measured by a dye-binding technique that utilizes the ability of albumin to form a stable complex with bromocresol green dye. The BCG-albumin complex

absorbs light at a different wavelength from the unbound dye. This method may overestimate albumin by binding to other proteins. (Rothschild, Oratz, Schreiber 2019)

Procedure

Label sufficient 13 × 100 mm test tubes for all samples, controls, calibrators, and a reagent blank. Using a 5 mL serological pipet, pipet 2.5 mL of BCG reagent into each tube. Pipet 10 µL of each sample, control or calibrator into the appropriate tubes. Add 10 µL of distilled water to the reagent blank tube. Mix all tubes by inversion.

Read the absorbance of each tube at 628 nm against the reagent blank and record your results on the data sheet. Calculate the albumin concentration of each sample in g/L using the absorbance/concentration proportion method.

2. 9. Globulin Estimation (g/L)

The globulin in the serum was estimated by the inhibition of antiglobulin antiserum method. Calculated globulin (total protein – albumin) is usually tested as part of a liver function test profile in both primary and secondary care and determines the serum globulin concentration, of which immunoglobulins are a major component. The main use hitherto of calculated globulin is to detect paraproteins when the level is high. This study investigated the potential to use low levels of calculated globulin to detect antibody deficiency.

2. 10. Growth Rate Estimation

Growth rate was calculated as the ratio of the weight gained during the treatment period to the number of days constituting the treatment period and was presented as percentage growth rate.

$$\text{Growth rat (\%)} = \frac{\text{Final body weight (g)} - \text{Initial body weight (g)}}{\text{Number of days}} \times 100\%$$

2. 11. Body Weight Increase Estimation

Initial and final weight of each rat was measured and the mean weight for each group was determined. Body weight increase was calculated as the ratio of change in the body during the treatment period to the initial weight and was presented as percentage body weight increase.

$$\text{Body weight increase (\%)} = \frac{\text{Final body weight (g)} - \text{Initial body weight (g)}}{\text{Initial body weight (g)}} \times 100\%$$

2. 12. Data Analysis

Data obtained were analyzed for statistical significance by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the Turkeys HSD post-hoc test is used to compare each of the test group with the control group as well as to compare the test groups for any significant difference in the effect of the treatment on the various parameters using SPSS package with significant level at ($p < 0.05$). Results are expressed as Mean±SEM.

3. RESULTS

The results of the administration of tramadol during sub-chronic alcoholic beverage (lager beer) consumption in Wistar rats are presented in Table 1.

3. 1. Percentage Body Weight Increase and Percentage Growth Rate (%)

The weight of the rats after 21 days of administration of tramadol and alcoholic beverage (lager beer) were obtained and compared with the initial weight measured before each treatment. The differences in weights were used to determine the percentage weight increase and growth rate during this period.

The value of the percentage body weight decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the tramadol group (1.13 ± 4.17), lager beer treated group (4.10 ± 1.84) and tramadol + lager beer treated group (-16.73 ± 2.18) compared to the control group (35.89 ± 7.10).

There was also a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in body weight in the group that was treated with lager beer and a significant decrease in group treated with tramadol + lager beer compared to the group treated with tramadol alone. A significant decrease in body weight in the group treated with tramadol + lager beer compared to the group treated with lager beer alone was also recorded.

Percentage growth rate decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the groups treated with tramadol (6.52 ± 23.63), lager beer (30.38 ± 12.54) and tramadol+lager beer (-90.40 ± 11.82) compared to the control group (156.29 ± 21.87). Percentage growth rate also increased significantly in the group treated with lager beer, decreased significantly in group treated with tramadol + lager beer compared to the group treated with tramadol alone. A significant decrease was also recorded in the group treated with tramadol + lager beer compared to the lager beer treated group.

Table 2. Growth rate and body weight increase of the different experimental groups.

Group	Treatment	Growth Rate (%)	Body weight increase (%)
Group 1	Normal control	156.29	35.89
		± 21.87	± 7.10
Group 2	Tramadol	6.52	1.13
		$\pm 23.63^*$	$\pm 4.17^*$
Group 3	Lager beer	30.38	4.10
		$\pm 12.54^*$	$\pm 2.71^*$
Group 4	Tramadol + lager beer	-91.40	-16.73
		$\pm 11.82^{*, a}$	$\pm 2.18^{*, a}$

Values are presented as mean \pm SEM, n = 6.

* = p < 0.05 vs group 1

a = p < 0.05 vs group 2

b = p < 0.05 vs group 3

3. 2. Serum Total Protein (g/L)

Serum total protein (g/l) decreased significantly (p < 0.05) in the tramadol treated group (61.83 \pm 0.40) compared to the control group (70.50 \pm 0.67). There were significant decrease (p < 0.05) in the lager beer treated group (66.83 \pm 0.31) and tramadol + lager beer treated group (64.83 \pm 0.95) compared to the control group. Administration of tramadol + lager beer caused a significant increase (p > 0.05) in serum total protein compared to the administration of tramadol alone. The tramadol + lager beer group also had a significant decrease (p < 0.05) in serum total protein compared to the lager beer treated group.

3. 3. Serum Albumin (g/L)

Serum albumin level was significantly decreased (p < 0.05) in the administered groups compared to the normal control group (NC) tramadol treated group (37.17 \pm 0.54), tramadol + lager beer treated group (35.67 \pm 0.42) and non-significantly reduced (p < 0.05) in the lager beer treated group (37.83 \pm 0.54) compared to the control group (43.00 \pm 0.89). Non-significant decrease in the serum albumin in the tramadol + lager beer treated group compared to the group on lager beer alone was also observed.

Table 3. Protein and Albumin Experimental Groups.

Group	Treatment	Total protein (g/L)	Albumin (g/L)
Group 1	Normal control	70.50	43.00
		\pm 0.67	\pm 0.89
Group 2	Tramadol	61.83	37.17
		\pm 0.40*	\pm 0.54*
Group 3	Lager beer	66.83	37.83
		\pm 0.31*, a	\pm 0.54*
Group 4	Tramadol + lager beer	64.83	35.67
		\pm 0.95*, a, b	\pm 0.42*

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 6.

* = significantly different from group 1 at p < 0.05

a = significantly different from group 2 at p < 0.05

b = significantly different from group 3 at p < 0.05

3. 4. Serum globulin (g/L)

Serum globulin level decreased non-significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the tramadol treated group (25.33 ± 0.61) and increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the group treated with lager beer (29.00 ± 0.26) and tramadol + lager beer treated group (29.17 ± 0.65) compared to the control group (27.50 ± 0.22). Significant increases in serum globulin level were recorded in the group treated with lager beer and tramadol + lager beer compared to the group treated with tramadol alone, there was also a significant increase in serum globulin level in the tramadol + lager beer treated group and lager beer treated group compared to the normal control group treated alone.

Table 4. Globulin Experimental Group.

Group	Treatment	Globulin (g/L)
Group 1	Normal control	27.50
		± 0.22
Group 2	Tramadol	25.33
		± 0.61
Group 3	Lager beer	29.00
		$\pm 0.26^{*, a}$
Group 4	Tramadol + lager beer	29.17
		$\pm 0.65^{*, a, b}$

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 6.

* = significantly different from group 1 at $p < 0.05$

a = significantly different from group 2 at $p < 0.05$

b = significantly different from group 3 at $p < 0.05$

4. DISCUSSION

From the result, administration of tramadol caused a significant reduction in serum total protein compared to the normal control and other treatment groups. However, treatment with tramadol + lager beer caused a decrease in serum total protein compared to the normal control, tramadol treated group and a significant reduction in serum total protein level compared to the group on lager beer alone WHO (2019) reported that heavy alcoholic beverage consumption affects protein synthesis. This significant increase in serum total protein level in the lager beer treated group may be attributed to the metabolic by product of alcohol (acetaldehyde) which is highly reactive, toxic, contribute to tissue damage, and may cause inflammation (Gregono et al, 2018).

From the result; treatment with tramadol, Lager beer as well as tramadol + Lager beer caused significant reduction in growth rate (%) and body weight increase (%) compared to the

control group. While treatment with tramadol +lager beer produced the least values in growth rate (%) and body weight increase (%), treatment with lager beer caused significantly high values while treatment with tramadol + lager beer had significantly lower values in growth rate (%) and body weight increase compared to other treatment groups (Carisa, 2018).

This reduction suggests that administration of tramadol can reduced growth rate (%) and body weight increase (%) in rats. Since the tramadol + lager beer treated group recorded lower values of growth rate (%) and body weight increase (%). This decrease suggest that tramadol + lager beer administration causes reduction in growth rate (%) and body weight increase (%). It has been reported that people who consume tramadol + lager beer are more likely to have loss of body mass index (BMI) than people who consume tramadol and lager beer separately.

The increase recorded in the lager beer treated group may be due to the fact that alcohol is a rich source of energy (7.1 k cal/g). It is therefore obvious that although tramadol + lager beer had a significant effect in reducing serum total protein, tramadol had a more significant impact. This is seen in the moderation of serum total protein level in the tramadol treated group. In this research, treatment with tramadol, lager beer as well as tramadol + lager beer caused significant reduction in serum bilirubin (conjugated and unconjugated) levels compared to the control group.

Serum globulin level decreased non-significantly in the tramadol treated group and increased significantly in the group treated with lager beer and tramadol + lager beer treated group compared to the control group. Significant increases in serum globulin level were recorded in the group treated with lager beer and tramadol + lager beer compared to the group treated with tramadol alone, there was also a significant increase in serum globulin level in the tramadol + lager beer treated group and lager beer treated group compared to the normal control group treated alone.

The reduction of serum WBC by tramadol, lager beer and tramadol + lager beer observed in this study suggest that their use suppresses the immune system and this could expose individuals that use the drugs (tramadol, lager beer as well as tramadol + lager beer) to infectious disease. Result of the serum electrolytes show that treatment with tramadol caused significant reduction in serum Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^- as well as significant elevation in serum Iron and HCO_3^- compared to the control group. These changes in serum electrolyte may be as a result of tissue damage due to the metabolism of tramadol (Klastsky, 2015).

Administration of lager beer caused significant reduction in serum Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- levels as well as significant elevation in serum Iron, and HCO_3^- levels compared to the control and tramadol treatment group. Although administration of tramadol + lager beer caused a significantly lower value for Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- as well as significantly higher value for serum HCO_3^- compared to the control and other treatment groups.

It also produced significantly lower value of Iron compared to the lager beer treated group and caused significantly low value of Iron compared to the control and tramadol treatment group. The reduction recorded in serum Na^+ , and K^+ , levels are however within the reference range Na^+ , (136-145 mmol/L), K^+ , (3.5-6 mmol/L). It is observed that treatment with tramadol, lager beer as well as tramadol + lager beer negatively impacted on serum calcium, iron and bicarbonate level. This agrees with an earlier report that high alcohol consumption affect the body's ability to balance calcium levels (De-Gaetano *et al.*, 2016).

Treatment with lager caused significantly higher values of serum TC and a significant reduction in LDL-C compared to the tramadol treated group. Although administration of tramadol + lager beer caused a significantly higher value for TC but an increase in LD1-C

compared to the control group; it also caused a significant decrease in serum HDL-C level compared to the control and other treatment groups. It is observed that treatment with lager beer positively impacted on serum HDL-C level.

This agrees with an earlier statement that alcohol consumption significantly impact on serum lipid profile (Jenson *et al.*, 1998). From the result, administration of tramadol caused a significant reduction in serum catalase compared to the control group. Treatment with lager beer caused a significant decrease in serum catalase compared to the control and tramadol treated group. However, treatment with tramadol + lager beer caused a very significant reduction in serum catalase level compared to the control group. It is observed that treatment with tramadol, lager beer as well as tramadol + lager beer significantly impact serum catalase level. In this study, administration of tramadol caused significant increase in serum GSH level compared to the control and a significant decrease compared to lager beer treated groups.

Treatment with lager beer caused a significant elevation in serum GSH level compared to the control group as well as significant increase in serum GSH level compared to other treatment groups. However, administration of tramadol + lager beer has a very significantly higher value in serum GSH compared to the control treatment group. It is believed that this elevation of serum GSH in the tramadol + lager beer treatment group observed in this study may be due to increased population of free radicals caused by combined administration of tramadol + lager beer.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Tramadol administration alongside sub chronic alcohol consumption may lead to alterations in total protein levels. These alterations could be influenced by the interaction between tramadol and alcohol metabolism, potentially affecting protein synthesis or degradation processes. Albumin levels may also be affected by the combined administration of tramadol and alcohol. Since albumin is a major protein synthesized in the liver, changes in its levels could reflect hepatic dysfunction or alterations in protein metabolism induced by tramadol and alcohol interaction.

Similarly, globulin levels may be impacted by tramadol administration during sub chronic alcohol consumption. Globulins play a crucial role in immune function and transport of substances in the bloodstream, and alterations in their levels could indicate immune system modulation or changes in protein distribution. The specific nature and extent of these biochemical effects may vary depending on factors such as dosage, duration of exposure, and individual variability among the rats studied.

The administration of tramadol causes reduction in growth rate (%) and body weight increase (%) as well as injury to the liver. Administration of lager beer lead to low white blood cells, elevated levels of catalase and glutathione, decrease blood platelets level, low sodium level and decrease in level of creatinine in the blood.

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